

KNOWLEDGE
WITHOUT
BOUNDARIES

EIFI 2020
ANNUAL
REPORT

WHERE WE WORK

In 2020, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 38 countries and ran projects in an additional 15 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 53 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Botswana, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe **ASIA PACIFIC** Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan **EUROPE** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Macedonia, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine **LATIN AMERICA** Chile, Colombia **MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA** Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

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**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

THE CHALLENGE

Access to knowledge is fundamental to education and research. It can break the cycle of poverty, improve employability and health, and promote sustainable development.

However, billions of people in developing and transition economy countries cannot benefit from the new opportunities knowledge provides due to factors such as the high cost of e-resources, legal barriers to accessing and using information, and poor telecommunications infrastructure.

OUR VISION

A world in which every person has the knowledge they need to achieve their full potential.

OUR MISSION

EIFL enables access to knowledge through libraries in developing and transition economy countries to support sustainable development.

OUR VALUES

EIFL embraces the following core values:

- Practical, sustainable, local solutions
- Collaboration and partnership
- Knowledge sharing
- Innovative approaches

WHAT WE DO

- We build capacity by organizing training events, developing tools and resources, and providing up-to-date information on issues that affect access to knowledge.
- We advocate for access to knowledge nationally and internationally.
- We encourage knowledge sharing through peer-to-peer learning, best practice case studies, our annual conference, and cooperation between library consortia.
- We initiate pilot projects for innovative library services.

OUR APPROACH

EIFL works to expand access to knowledge in a cost-effective and sustainable way by supporting the establishment and development of strong national library consortia.

Library consortia in 38 countries in Africa, Asia and Europe, representing almost 3,000 libraries, have joined the EIFL network.

OUR CORE INITIATIVES

- **Access to Knowledge for Education, Learning and Research** – ensuring well-resourced libraries, modern information and communications technology (ICT) infrastructure and skilled staff to provide essential support to students and researchers.
- **Access to Knowledge for Sustainable Livelihoods** – helping to transform people's lives through innovative services in public libraries.

OUR PROGRAMMES

Licensing Programme (EIFL-Licensing)

Negotiates affordable access to commercial e-resources and research support services. In addition, the programme negotiates affordable open access publishing terms for authors.

Copyright and Libraries Programme (EIFL-IP)

Advocates for national and international copyright law reform, and supports librarians to become advocates for a fair copyright system.

Open Access Programme (EIFL-OA)

Removes barriers to knowledge sharing by advocating for the adoption of open access and open science policies, by building capacity to set up and enhance open access journals and repositories, and by improving researchers' open science skills.

Public Library Innovation Programme (EIFL-PLIP)

Advances community development by enabling public libraries to implement innovative ideas that use technology to improve people's lives and livelihoods.

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

2020 took us all by surprise. In March, due to COVID-19, the institutions that we work with closed down, travel restrictions were introduced and the pandemic forced everyone to reorganize their operations and move online.

We adapted quickly, replacing scheduled in-person meetings and training with 149 virtual workshops, meetings, and conferences.

Academic libraries had to continue to support faculty and students, who were working and studying remotely from their homes, presenting serious challenges for many libraries in our 38 partner countries lacking sufficient IT infrastructure or funding to install remote access systems.

We asked our publisher partners and content aggregators to allow off-campus access to paywalled e-books, journals and databases via username & password. Some responded positively, offering temporary access. Also, 104 institutions in 11 countries took advantage of EIFL-negotiated discounted pricing and subscribed to RemoteXs, a technical solution for remote access to licensed e-resources. Together we were able to continue serving the needs of faculty and students, despite the challenges: in 2020 over 6 million full text articles and book chapters were downloaded by library users in our partner countries.

We supported the efforts of the global scientific community to find treatments and a vaccine for COVID-19. With our partners in the OpenAIRE project, we curated COVID-19 related research outputs via the OpenAIRE COVID-19 Gateway and the Coronavirus Disease Research Community –

COVID-19 on Zenodo. We also joined global advocacy calling for an intellectual property regime that supports rather than hinders efforts to tackle COVID-19.

Our 2020 EIFL Public Library Innovation Award call focused on public library responses to the pandemic. We selected four winners: a library using 3D printers to create hands-free door openers to reduce COVID-19 infection; a telephone reading service for the elderly; online video art classes for children, and library services via Facebook.

In July we launched the Myanmar Education, Research and Learning (MERAL) Portal, which by the end of 2020, provided open access to almost 6,000 research outputs from 24 universities. We were delighted by the interest of other universities in joining the MERAL Portal, and we were looking forward to working with them in 2021. However, political events have intervened, and our hearts go out to our colleagues and partners in Myanmar.

In November, the EIFL Copyright and Libraries Programme turned 15, and we marked the occasion with a campaign showcasing the programme's achievements. This Annual Report features one of the programme's most successful initiatives – advocacy for ratification of the Marrakesh Treaty, which increases access to knowledge for people with print disabilities.

I hope you enjoy this report. Thank you to everyone – our partners and funders, our board members and our staff – who help to bring us closer to achieving our vision.

– Rima Kuprytė, Director of EIFL

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas

THE RIGHT TO READ

FOR PEOPLE WITH
PRINT DISABILITIES

EIFL's support for ratification and
implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty

Photo by Khasar Shandag

“For generations, visually impaired people have had their requests for accessible format books declined because the books were simply not available. With the rights gained under the Marrakesh Treaty, our community is becoming braver about asking for books. It is like a new beginning!”

– INGA DAVIDONIENĖ, DIRECTOR, LITHUANIAN LIBRARY FOR THE BLIND

When word came through that negotiators had reached agreement on the text for the Marrakesh Treaty for persons with print disabilities, delegates attending the WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization) Diplomatic Conference in Marrakesh in June 2013 burst into spontaneous outpourings of joy.

The treaty, which took five years of tough negotiations, marked the start of the end of the book famine for blind and visually impaired people – the fact that only 7% of the world’s printed materials are available in accessible formats, like braille, audio, large print and digital accessible formats.

The treaty – full name, Marrakesh Treaty to Facilitate Access to Published Works for Persons Who Are Blind, Visually Impaired, or Otherwise Print Disabled – removes legal barriers to copying books and other copyright-protected works into accessible formats, and to sharing them across borders. EIFL actively supported the World Blind Union in negotiations at WIPO headquarters in Geneva that led to the ‘miracle of Marrakesh’. Now work to deliver on the promise of the Marrakesh Treaty, to help end the book famine, has moved to national level. There are three stages: a country must agree to join the treaty, then the treaty’s provisions are usually implemented into national law, and libraries should gear up to make use of their new rights under the treaty.

EIFL has been working hard on all fronts in partner countries, raising awareness among librarians and policy-makers, supporting advocacy campaigns, organizing seminars,

responding to government consultations, and publishing specialist guides for librarians. Our two key guides, *The Marrakesh Treaty: An EIFL Guide for Libraries* (2014), published in nine languages, and *Getting Started. Implementing the Marrakesh Treaty for persons with print disabilities. A practical guide for librarians* (2018), available in five languages, have been downloaded almost 2,000 times from the EIFL website.

By December 2020, the treaty had reached a major milestone – over 100 countries had joined, among them 23 EIFL partner countries. Fourteen EIFL partner countries have begun or already completed implementation of the treaty into national law, and libraries are starting to realize the benefits for print-disabled patrons.

ZIMBABWE: ‘KNOW YOUR RIGHTS’

Zimbabwe joined the Marrakesh Treaty in 2019. Now the provisions are being implemented into national law, and in 2020, EIFL and the Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC) submitted comments on the copyright amendment bill. Rosemary Maturure, EIFL’s Copyright Coordinator in Zimbabwe, says university libraries are getting ready to provide expanded services for visually impaired people.

“We are raising awareness about the treaty so that visually impaired people know their rights, through university exhibitions, national disability events, conferences, and through our library websites. At the same time our libraries are dedicating staff for serving visually impaired students, and some librarians have attended online training

in the latest techniques in accessible book production, such as braille, audio, e-text and large print formats, offered by WIPO’s ABC Accessible Publishing initiative.”

SUCCESS IN KYRGYZSTAN

In 2017, Kyrgyzstan became the first EIFL partner country to both ratify the Marrakesh Treaty and implement it into national law, following a successful advocacy campaign led by EIFL’s partner, the Kyrgyz Library and Information Consortium (KLIC). Librarian Sania Battalova, who was the Vice-president of KLIC and EIFL’s Country Coordinator in Kyrgyzstan, remembers the Marrakesh Treaty campaign as one of the most exciting and rewarding periods in her career.

“The needs in Kyrgyzstan were great. The Republican Library for the Blind and Deaf lacked financial support, and it had limited braille and digital collections. There were no textbooks in accessible formats for university students, or accessible format e-resources. And librarians were nervous about creating accessible texts because of copyright law.

“In 2014, EIFL engaged a Kyrgyz law firm, ARTE, to translate EIFL’s guide to the Marrakesh Treaty into Russian. At the same time, the lawyers examined Kyrgyzstan’s copyright law to see what changes were needed to bring it into line with the treaty. Bringing librarians and legal professionals to work together was a great step: we now understood the treaty and had a vision for how the copyright law should be adapted. So we were able to advocate for two steps at once – ratification of the treaty and copyright law reform.

“Kyrgyzstan is a small country and this worked in our favour: library directors know each other, and – very importantly – we have professional connections with people in the national copyright office. We began our campaign, meeting with officials and lawmakers, but progress was slow.

“Then, in 2015, with support from EIFL, we received a grant from the Soros Foundation-Kyrgyzstan for a country-wide campaign for open education and free access to knowledge, and also for copyright law reform. The campaign was called, ‘The Right to Read, Right to Knowledge’.

“This was our breakthrough, and from that moment it was non-stop action. We held many meetings and seminars, reaching out to Members of Parliament (MPs), government officials, lawyers, non-governmental organizations. “We were very lucky that MP Dastan Bekeshev, the first blind person to be elected to parliament, strongly supported the campaign. Dastan introduced the Marrakesh Treaty to other MPs, and emphasized its importance to the community.

“In February 2016, we organized the first-ever conference in Kyrgyzstan on copyright, ‘Copyright in the Digital Age: Access to Information and Knowledge’. All the players met together – international advisors, MPs, government ministries, libraries and societies for the blind, copyright officials, and legal experts. The conference was the key to our success because other stakeholders started to view libraries as serious partners in copyright law reform.

"Afterwards, we continued to work with ARTE law firm, drafting proposals for amendments. MP Dastan supported our amendments and ensured that they were included in the copyright bill (2016). We waited anxiously over the next months – and in March 2017, were overjoyed to hear that the President had signed the bill into law. And all our proposed amendments were included!

"To complete the legal process, the government should also accede to the Marrakesh Treaty. In May 2017, we were delighted when the government deposited its instrument of accession at WIPO, and three months later, in August, the Marrakesh Treaty entered into force in Kyrgyzstan. From now on, librarians would not be forced to turn down requests for accessible format texts because of copyright. At last, blind and visually impaired people in Kyrgyzstan had equal rights of access to information.

"In 2018, to show the Marrakesh Treaty in action, we facilitated the first-ever international transfer of accessible format books to Kyrgyzstan during a national seminar in Bishkek organized by WIPO in cooperation with the State Service of Intellectual Property and Innovation (Kyrgyzpatent). The requested titles were converted into digital accessible format by the University of Toronto Libraries, Canada and transferred to Kyrgyzstan using Dropbox. In that seminar, we showed how straightforward international exchange of accessible books can be.

"Our success in ratifying the treaty and amending our copyright law was the result of a collective effort by many passionate and involved organizations and individuals, including libraries. We are extremely thankful for their hard work."

Now new services for persons with print disabilities are being rolled out nationwide. The Republican Library for Children and Youth, a public library in the capital Bishkek, is leading efforts to develop a national library infrastructure for accessible books. The library has developed practical manuals on

how to convert printed works into accessible formats, and has provided training.

"Now we are working towards creating a national catalogue of accessible books. All our libraries in Kyrgyzstan have access to the catalogue, and can request material needed from other libraries. In this way, blind and visually impaired people will have access to resources from across the country. And if we do not have the book needed in Kyrgyzstan, for the first time, we can request it from another country," says Nyriyla Sarybaeva, head of the library's training centre.

LITHUANIA: 'A TRULY GLOBAL SERVICE'

Lithuania has also joined and implemented the treaty into national law. By enabling cross-border sharing of accessible format material, the Marrakesh Treaty dramatically expands opportunities for learning and research for visually impaired people. In 2020, Inga Davidonienė, Director of the Lithuanian Library for the Blind, received an unexpected request from a student in Delhi in India.

"The student is studying Indo-European languages. Lithuanian is a very old language that belongs to the family of Indo-European languages, and he needed books in Lithuanian. He selected 14 audio books from a list we provided. I was so happy to help. Such an experience gives us confidence that we are moving in the right direction in serving visually impaired scholars. We are becoming a truly global service!

"In 2020 we organized five seminars for Lithuanian librarians, where our specialists shared knowledge, experience and guidelines for practical implementation of the treaty. More than 300 public and academic librarians took part.

"It is very important for Lithuanian libraries to know that they can also serve readers who cannot read print text. Our aspiration is that all print disabled readers who come to any Lithuanian library will receive the information they need."

The Marrakesh Treaty – EIFL's contribution

20 countries joined the treaty

- Azerbaijan • Belarus • Botswana
- Estonia • Ghana • Kenya
- Kyrgyzstan • Latvia • Lesotho
- Lithuania • Moldova • Mongolia
- Poland • Russia • Serbia
- Slovenia • Tanzania • Thailand
- Uganda • Zimbabwe

23 copyright law recommendations

- Belarus • Botswana • Brazil
- Côte d'Ivoire • Ethiopia
- European Union • Ireland
- Kenya • Kyrgyzstan • Lesotho
- Lithuania • Malawi • Mongolia
- Myanmar • Nepal
- North Macedonia • Russia
- Serbia • South Africa • Tanzania
- Uganda • Zanzibar • Zimbabwe

37 million blind and visually impaired people have greater access to knowledge.*

People living with perceptual impairment such as dyslexia, and physical disabilities that prevent them from holding or turning the pages of a book, also benefit from the Marrakesh Treaty. Global statistics for these beneficiaries are not available.

Thank you to the Open Society Foundations for supporting our work in the area, and to UNESCO and the University of Toronto Scarborough for supporting regional training events.

* Bourne R, Steinmetz J, Flaxman S, et al., *Trends in prevalence of blindness and distance and near vision impairment over 30 years: an analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study*. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020. Accessed via the IAPB Vision Atlas (<https://www.iapb.org/learn/vision-atlas>).

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their lives
and the lives of others

YUSUF GANYANA JUMA

SENIOR ICT OFFICER, KENYA NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICE KENYA

Yusuf Ganyana Juma is based at Kibera Public Library, which serves people living in Kibera, a slum on the outskirts of Kenya's capital city, Nairobi. "Many people come to the library to ask for help in seeking employment. But they are missing opportunities because they do not have digital skills," said Yusuf.

In 2018 Yusuf was one of 12 ICT Officers selected by Kenya National Library Service to undergo an intensive EIFL training-of-trainers programme that combined generic training skills with digital and mobile literacy skills. The training changed Yusuf's life.

"Before, I wanted nothing to do with training, I only did it when instructed, and I was a terrible trainer. Through EIFL I learnt how to group trainees according to age and skills levels; how to make training interactive; how to use icebreakers, and a lot more.

"I have expanded the ICT skills course our library offers to include job seeking, marketing your skills online, and life skills like time management. Now, so many people are coming for training that we have a waiting list," he said.

In-person training scheduled for 2020 was interrupted by COVID-19. However, Yusuf kept in touch with his trainees through social media and continued to train and mentor them online.

In 2020: Fifteen librarians who completed the EIFL training-of-trainers programme trained almost 1,000 librarians in Kenya, Namibia, Uganda and Zambia to introduce ICT-based services in their libraries.

"Since the EIFL training, I am always on the lookout for opportunities for training for my community."

– YUSUF GANYANA JUMA

TATJANA TIMOTIJEVIĆ

HEAD OF DEPARTMENT OF SCIENTIFIC INFORMATION, NATIONAL LIBRARY SERBIA

KoBSON, EIFL's partner library consortium in Serbia, has 66 member institutions and is hosted by the National Library. One of Tatjana Timotijević's responsibilities is negotiating with publishers for access to e-resources for KoBSON members. Tatjana is also EIFL Country Coordinator in Serbia.

KoBSON subscribes to e-resources from 17 content providers. These are well used: in 2020, there were over 1.8 million full-text downloads from these e-resources. Serbia's research output is also high: over 4,000 articles are published by corresponding authors from Serbia annually in Web of Science indexed journals.

The number of articles published in open access grew from 32% in 2017 to 40% in 2020. To encourage this trend, KoBSON negotiated agreements with Cambridge University Press for 2020 and 2021 that include open access publishing terms for their authors.

KoBSON authors have also been benefiting from the agreements that EIFL negotiates.

"Through the EIFL agreements our researchers have the opportunity to publish in open access at waived or discounted article processing charges (APCs) in 1,176 journals," said Tatjana.

"We are a small team at KoBSON and do not have the capacity or time to negotiate these complex agreements ourselves, nor do we have contacts with all the publishers where Serbian authors publish," she said.

In 2020: EIFL agreements with 10 publishers enabled authors in our partner countries to publish for free or at reduced APCs in 1,523 journals.

"We are extremely happy to be able to take advantage of EIFL's open access publishing agreements with journal publishers."

– TATJANA TIMOTIJEVIĆ

DICK KAWOOYA

ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR, SCHOOL OF INFORMATION SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH CAROLINA

USA

Dick Kawooya was studying at Makerere University, Uganda, when he was appointed as EIFL Copyright Coordinator for Uganda by the Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL).

In June 2005, Dick became the first African librarian to take part in copyright negotiations at WIPO (the World Intellectual Property Organization) when he was invited to join EIFL's delegation to the Second Session of the Inter-sessional Intergovernmental Meeting on a Development Agenda of WIPO which took place in Geneva, Switzerland.

"It was probably the most consequential event I ever attended because it was at that meeting that I noted the great need for empirical evidence from Africa to support policy work at public forums like WIPO."

This realization prompted Dick to develop the African Copyright and Access to Knowledge Project, with other partners, which received international funding to enable a research team from eight African countries to examine the extent to which copyright laws in their countries supported access to knowledge.

In the intervening years, Dick's relationship with EIFL led to other opportunities for research, training and engagement with policy-makers. Now Dick is recognized as an international expert on copyright and advises EIFL on copyright reform in Africa.

In 2020: EIFL attended two WIPO meetings and made five interventions in support of copyright laws that maximize access to knowledge.

"African copyright laws are lagging behind and hinder library activities. At that first WIPO meeting it became clear that we needed to do research to make a strong case for policy makers. And that really shaped my career."

– DICK KAWOOYA

RICHARD BRUCE LAMPTEY

**LIBRARIAN, COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERSITY OF
SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
GHANA**

In 2020, EIFL and our partner library consortium, the Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH), launched a training programme to raise librarians' and researchers' awareness about open access and open science and to stimulate advocacy for adoption of open science policies.

"Currently, just the CSIR and the university where I work have adopted open access policies," said Richard Bruce Lamptey, EIFL's Country Coordinator in Ghana.

"The COVID-19 pandemic put a stop to face-to-face training, so with EIFL we organized six webinars.

"Over 550 people took part, including many librarians and researchers who might not have been able to travel to in-person events.

"Already I can see changes. Our librarians are more able to advise researchers about publishing in quality open access journals, and how to avoid predatory publishers.

"Our researchers are more careful about where they publish – they prefer open access journals that have greater visibility and bring more citations. And more researchers are using ORCID to identify themselves, which improves attribution, recognition and discoverability of research outputs."

In 2020: In Europe, EIFL, with OpenAIRE and other partners, organized more than 100 open science training events reaching over 13,500 librarians, researchers and students.

"Together, EIFL and CARLIGH have succeeded in building new open science champions. In 2021 we will create a roadmap for future development of institutional and national open science policies, infrastructure and skills in Ghana."

– RICHARD BRUCE LAMPTEY

OUR NETWORK

EIFL partner library consortia nominate coordinators who serve as the main point of contact between EIFL's Programmes and their consortium. In their countries, they lead and facilitate activities initiated by EIFL, and have been central to our success and achievements over the years.

We would like to thank all our Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2020.

ALBANIA

Consortium of Albanian Libraries

Country Coordinator: Albana Velianj
Licensing Coordinators: Renata Bardhi and Mirlona Buzo

ARMENIA

Digital Library Association of Armenia (DLAA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Anna Chulyan
Copyright Coordinator: Hasmik Galstyan
Open Access Coordinator: Tigran Zakaryan

AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan Library and Information Consortium for Availability of Electronic Information (AzLIC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Jamila Yusifova

BELARUS

Council of Belarusian Libraries on Information Cooperation (BelCoLib)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Viatcheslav Britchkovski
Copyright Coordinator: Viktor Pshibytko
Licensing Coordinator: Mariya Domovskaja

BOTSWANA

Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Naniki Maphakwane
Copyright Coordinator: Khutsafalo Kadimo
Open Access Coordinator: Bobana Badisang

CHINA

Library Network of the Chinese Academy of Sciences

Country Coordinator: Xiwen Liu
Open Access Coordinator: Kunhua Zhao
Copyright Coordinator: Elsa Luo (until August)

CONGO

Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (COBAC)

Country Coordinator: Eliezer Mwongane
Licensing Coordinator: Jean Baptiste Unen

ESTONIA

Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Marika Meltsas
Copyright Coordinator: Karmen Linask
Open Access Coordinator: Elena Sipria-Mironov

ETHIOPIA

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL)

Country Coordinator: Derib Erget Mamuye
Copyright Coordinator: Ato Yoseph Bizuneh
Licensing Coordinators: Bedassa Motuma Beyene and Derib Erget Mamuye
Open Access Coordinator: Solomon Mekonnen Tekle

FIJI

Fiji Library Consortium

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Udyia Shukla

GEORGIA

Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) 2017

Country Coordinator: Irakli Garibashvili
Licensing Coordinator: Marika Zhorzholiani

GHANA

Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH)

Country Coordinator: Richard Bruce Lamptey
Copyright Coordinator: Teresa Adu
Licensing Coordinator: Mac Anthony Cobblah
Open Access Coordinator: Donyina Fokuo and Nana Tuhufo Quagraine

IVORY COAST

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur de Cote d'Ivoire (COBES-CI)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Cécile Coulibaly
Copyright Coordinator: Ahou Marie-Claire Allou
Open Access Coordinator: Adjoh Hortense Kakpo epse Outtara

KENYA

Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Arnold Mwanzu
Copyright Coordinator: Janegrace Kinyanjui
Open Access Coordinator: George Njoroge

KOSOVO

Consortium of Electronic Libraries in Kosovo (CELK)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Bukurije Haliti

KYRGYZSTAN

Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jyldyz Bekbalaeva
Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Safia Rafikova
Licensing Coordinator: Iryna Pak

LAOS

Laos Library and Information Consortium (LALIC)

Country, Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Sypha Phongsavath
Open Access Coordinator: Sisavanh Linsavath

LATVIA

Culture Information Systems Centre

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Agrita Sagalajeva
Copyright Coordinator: Inta Mikluna

LESOTHO

Lesotho Library Consortium (LELICO)

Country Coordinator: Mapasane Lephoto (until July); Buhle Mbambo-Thata (from July)
Copyright Coordinator: Pontso Mkuebe (from September)
Licensing Coordinator: Tahleho Tseole
Open Access Coordinator: Matseliso Kabeli

LITHUANIA

Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Ausra Vaskeviciene
Copyright Coordinator: Janina Marcinkeviciene
Open Access Coordinator: Gintare Tautkeviciene

MALAWI

Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Geoffrey Francis Salanje
Open Access Coordinator: Fiskani Ngwira

MALDIVES

(No name – under development)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Aminath Shiuna

MOLDOVA

Electronic Resources for Moldova (REM)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Silvia Ghinculov (until December); Elena Tudor Railean (from December)
Copyright Coordinator: Mariana Harjevschi
Open Access Coordinator: Natalia Cheradi

NAMIBIA

Namibia Library Consortium (NALICO)

Country Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks
Licensing Coordinator: Namutenya Hamwaalwa

NEPAL

Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Jagadish Aryal

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonian e-Libraries (MEL)

Country, Licensing & Copyright Coordinator: Miodrag Dadasovic

PALESTINE

Palestinian Library and Information Consortium (PALICO)

Country Coordinators: Diana Sayej Naser; Rami Alhindawi for Gaza
Licensing Coordinator: Diana Sayej Naser
Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Mohammad Abu Hamdieh

SENEGAL

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Youssoupha Gueye
Copyright Coordinator: Awa Diouf Cisse
Open Access Coordinator: Mandiaye Ndiaye

SERBIA

Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON)

Country Coordinator: Tatjana Timotijevic
Licensing Coordinators: Tatjana Timotijevic and Boris Denadic
Copyright Coordinator: Dragana Milunovic
Open Access Coordinator: Milica Sevkusic

SLOVENIA

Consortium of Slovene Electronic Collections (COSEC)

Country Coordinator: Karmen Stular Sotosek
Licensing Coordinator: Herman Erculj
Open Access Coordinator: Alenka Kavcic-Colic

SUDAN

Sudanese Academic Libraries Consortium (SALC)

Country Coordinator: Iman Abdelrahman
Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Abdelaziz Gabir
Open Access Coordinator: Rania M. Hassan Baleela

TANZANIA

Consortium of Tanzania Universities and Research Libraries (COTUL)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Paul Samwel Muneja
Licensing Coordinator: Cyrill Ndekakao

THAILAND

Electronic Information for Libraries in Thailand (eifl-Thailand)

Country, Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Soeythip Sukul
Open Access Coordinator: Adisak Sukul

UGANDA

Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL)

Country Coordinator: David Bukenya
Copyright Coordinator: Eric Haumba
Licensing Coordinator: Thecla Atukwase
Open Access Coordinator: Hassan Ssengooba

UKRAINE

Association 'Informatio-Consortium'

Country, Copyright, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Oleksii Vasyliiev

UZBEKISTAN

EIFL Uzbekistan Consortium

Country Coordinator: Gavhar Hamdamova (until October); Gulrukh Iskandarova (from October)
Licensing Coordinator: Dilshod Usmanaliev (until October); Alisher Kattavekov (from October)
Open Access Coordinator: Maksim Savochkin

ZAMBIA

Zambia Library Consortium (ZALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Eness Chitumbo
Copyright Coordinator: Benson Njobvu
Open Access Coordinator: Pilate Chewe

ZIMBABWE

Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC)

Country & Copyright Coordinator: Katherine Matsika
Licensing Coordinator: Audrey Mhlanga (until October); Sarlomie Zinyemba (from October)
Open Access Coordinator: Plaxedes Chaitezvi

OUR TEAM

Meeting of the EIFL network during the General Assembly held virtually from 30 September – 1 October 2020.

STAFF

Andrius Kriščiūnas, Finance Manager
Aung Kyaw Soe, eLibrary Myanmar Project Coordinator for Mandalay
Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator
Gwen Franck, Open Access Programme Coordinator
Iryna Kuchma, Open Access Programme Manager
Jean Fairbairn, Communications Manager, Website and Publications
Jevgenija Ševcova, Programmes and Events Coordinator
Louise Stoddard, Communications Manager

Myat Sann Nyein, eLibrary Myanmar Project Coordinator for Yangon
Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager
Rima Kuprytė, Director
Romy Beard, Licensing Programme Manager
Susan Schnuer, Public Library Innovation Programme Capacity Building Manager
Teresa Hackett, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager
Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Arnold Hirshon, Chairperson, Kelvin Smith Library, Case Western Reserve University, USA
Adam Hyde, Founder of Coko, Book Sprints, Paged.js, Open Publishing Awards and the Open Publishing Fest (from July 2020)
Emilija Banionytė, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania
Jyldyz Bekbalaeva, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan
Joel Sam, African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AFLIA), Ghana
Winston Tabb, The Sheridan Libraries, The John Hopkins University, USA (until July 2020)

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL INCOME AND EXPENDITURE 2020

INCOME	€	%
• Programme income	2,979,391	81.8%
• Participation fees	366,532	10.1%
• General Support	207,095	5.7%
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	90,294	2.4%

Total **3,643,312**

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	970,312	88.7%
• Personnel & contracted expenses	102,415	9.4%
• Operating expenses	20,929	1.9%

Total **1,093,656**

**COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR
2021 TO 2023 PROGRAMME DELIVERY** **2,534,843**

CONTINUITY RESERVE **308,308**

OUR FUNDERS

We would like to thank the following organizations and individuals for their generous support for our work in 2020:

- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- ChronosHub
- Embassy of Denmark, Myanmar
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme
- GE2P2 Global Foundation
- Individual donors through GlobalGiving
- Luxembourg Development Cooperation Agency (LuxDev)
- Open Society Foundations
- Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies (ATHENA RC)
- UNESCO
- University of Luxembourg (UNILU)
- Wehubit Programme (implemented by the Belgian development agency, Enabel)

EVENTS

In 2020, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 149 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- Webinar: Monitoring the cost of Open Access
- Public Domain Day (Washington D.C., USA)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE Research Graph
- US Trade Representative public hearing on South Africa (Washington D.C., USA)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE Graph
- Open science policy workshop for Romania (Bucharest, Romania)
- Consortium Building Workshop for Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (Bunia, Democratic Republic of the Congo)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Open Science and Open Data in promoting research outputs

FEBRUARY

- Webinar: OpenAIRE on open access how to and why
- Webinar: Enrich your DSpace repository with customized tools
- Introduction to MERAL Portal and Training (Mandalay and Yangon, Myanmar)
- MERAL Portal agreement signing ceremony (Yangon, Myanmar)
- Young African Library Innovators study tour (Nashville, USA)
- Public Library Association 2020 Conference (Nashville, USA)
- EIFL visit to National University of Laos (Vientiane, Lao People's Democratic Republic)
- Workshop for trainers in EOSC projects (Amsterdam, Netherlands)
- EOSC Skills and Training Working Group kick-off meeting (Brussels, Belgium)
- Webinar: CORE free discovery tools for libraries
- Webinar: How to claim Cambridge University Press APC waivers & discounts
- Webinar: CORE overview for Palestine

APRIL

- Webinar: Developments in open access books
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on COVID-19 tools, activities, best practices and contact points in Greece
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Open Science, FAIR principles for RDM, Horizon 2020 requirements and EOSC
- Webinar: OpenAIRE updates for Turkey
- COAR General Assembly (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on legal perspective on RDM

MAY

- Webinar: OpenAIRE on GDPR and Research – Where We Stand
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Open Research Gateway for the ELIXIR-GR Infrastructure
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Data and AI
- Webinar: OpenAIRE updates for Hungary

- Webinar: OpenAIRE on cooperative non-APC publishing models
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on open access in earth and environmental sciences
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on dashboard for Turkish repository managers
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on developments around Plan S

JUNE

- OR2020 Conference (Online)
- Workshop: Open Repositories 2020 (Online)
- Webinar: Subscription cancellations and alternative access options
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Amnesia
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on interoperability in EOSC – OpenAIRE Guidelines for repositories
- Webinar: Pursuing open at Iowa State University
- Ghana open science trainers' meet-up (Online)
- Training National University of Laos Faculty of Law researchers to use e-resources (Online)
- Webinar: Gigabit Libraries Network – DIY Wireless and ICT Challenges Worldwide
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on GDPR and legal issues in RDM
- Co-designing open access publishing infrastructures meeting (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE report, 'Towards Sustainable Cooperative and Non-APC Publishing Models
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on transformative agreements

- OpenAIRE virtual coffee break
- OR2020: Ideas Challenge (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE Citizen Science activities in Education

JULY

- WIPO Conversation on Intellectual Property and AI (Online)
- Webinar: Open access journals and publishers
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on intellectual property and open science
- Webinar: E-resources during COVID-19 – copyright and licensing issues
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on open science and COVID-19
- Co-designing open access publishing infrastructures meeting (Online)

AUGUST

- Training of the National University of Laos Faculty of Law researchers to use e-resources (Online)
- Webinar: Institutional repository management
- Virtual WSIS Forum: Co-creating innovative learning
- Open Science skills profile development workshop for librarians in Africa (Online)
- Regional Round Table for Europe on IFLA's Governance Review (Online)
- Co-designing open access publishing infrastructures meeting (Online)
- Use of e-resources training for librarians from Yangon University of Education (Online)

- Three training events on MERAL Portal for six Myanmar universities (Online)
- Open Science Summer School, Switzerland (Online)

SEPTEMBER

- US-Kenya Free Trade Agreement: briefing for civil society working group (Online)
- Webinar: ORCID
- Webinar: Persistent Identifiers
- Asia Open Access Meeting 2020 (Online)
- WIPO Virtual Conference on the Global Digital Content Market
- Two MERAL Portal training events for three Myanmar universities (Online)
- OASPA Conference 2020 (Online)
- WIPO Assemblies 2020 (Online)
- IFLA CLM mid-term meeting (Online)
- Occupy Library conference (Online)
- Scientific Exhibition: Science is Wonderful! 2020 (Online)
- #WeMissiPRES Festival (Online)
- UNESCO Regional Consultation on Open Science for Eastern Europe (Online)
- Moldova Open Science training (Online)
- Armenia Open Science training (Online)
- #RRI4REAL – FIT4RRI Virtual Summit (Online)
- EIFL General Assembly (Online)
- Webinar: Transatlantic Consumer Dialogue – Controlled Digital Lending in a Pandemic

OCTOBER

- 2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop (Online)
- Workshop: Pandemic-Proof Libraries – Lessons from COVID-19 (Online)
- Webinar: Gigabit Libraries Network – P4PA 2020 Declaration ‘Every Community Connected’
- Webinar: RDM services
- African Digital Storytelling Symposium (Online)
- Conference: University Library at a new stage of social communications development (Online)

- OpenAIRE Week and General Assembly (Online)
- Workshop: LIBSENSE Arab Region Progress & Perspectives (Online)
- Meeting with UNESCO Permanent Delegations on the first draft of the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (Online)
- EOSC Governance Symposium 2020 (Online)
- Botswana Open University Open Access Week Workshop (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on making research more visible and connected
- Webinar: Nazarbayev University Library – Research Data Management and Open Access to publications and data
- EIFL, COAR, OpenAIRE Panel discussion: Equity and inclusion: community-owned infrastructures for open science (Online)
- Open Access Week Kyrgyzstan (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on scholarly publishing and open access
- Webinar: OpenAIRE/Eurodoc on open science ambassadors – how can early career researchers boost open science?
- Webinar: OpenAIRE – Towards a scholarly commons
- Qatar National Library Panel discussion: Open Access in the time of COVID-19 (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on research data – accessible infrastructures and innovative tools in Greece
- Open Access Week Russia (Online)
- COAR, EIFL, OpenAIRE Panel discussion: Equity and inclusion – open science policies (Online)
- Webinar: LIBSENSE on repository interoperability and harvesting
- The Australian eResearch & Data Skills Summit 2020 (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE updates for Latvia
- University of Johannesburg Panel discussion: Open with Purpose – Taking Action to Build Structural Equity and Inclusion (Online)

- CLACSO consultation on Latin American research assessment (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on organizing GDPR compliant online events
- Workshop: Training Resource Catalogue Interoperability

NOVEMBER

- FAIRIO Workshop: Accessibility of Research Information (Online)
- GÉANT Infoshare: Open Access and Publishing (Online)
- Internet Governance Forum (IGF) 2020 (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on COVID-19 – best practices, tools and contact points in Greece
- Co-designing open access publishing infrastructures workflow sprint (Online)
- cOAlition S Rights Retention Strategy Summit meeting for research support organizations (Online)
- Webinar: Creative Commons licenses in teaching and learning
- UKSG Conference (Online)
- Dragons’ Lair, WIPO Copyright Committee (40th session) side event (Online)
- WIPO Copyright Committee (40th session) (Online)
- Webinar: ALA International Relations Round Table – EIFL’s strategy for public library development in Kenya and Namibia
- The Munin Conference (Online)
- Webinar: Research Assessment
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on use of Creative Commons licences for research and education
- Three MERAL Portal training events for six Myanmar universities (Online)
- ICOLC Europe (Online)
- Co-designing OA publishing infrastructures workflow sprint (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Open Science Practices
- Open Access Week Côte d’Ivoire (Online)
- Georgia Open Science training (Online)

- Mini-conference: LIBSENSE Francophone Africa Day (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Amnesia
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on COVID-19

DECEMBER

- Six MERAL Portal training events for 30 Myanmar universities (Online)
- OpenAIRE virtual coffee break
- Webinar: OpenAIRE – Open Science & RDM for CHIST-ERA beneficiaries
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Open Science in Horizon 2020
- Webinar: OpenAIRE on Galaxy – an open infrastructure for biological data analysis
- Webinar: WITS University and ReCreate SA – Open with Purpose: Taking Action to Build Structural Equity and Inclusion
- EUA and OpenAIRE workshop: University Approaches to Citizen Science Workshop (Online)
- Webinar: Open access policy development in India
- OA2020 Update and Summit of Chief Negotiators (Online)
- e-AGE20 conference (Online)
- 5th ESAC Workshop – Smoothing the path to open access (Online)
- Training of the National University of Laos Faculty of Law librarians to use e-resources (Online)

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to make knowledge more accessible. In 2020, we worked with the following partners:

- Access Now
- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA)
- Arab Federation of Libraries and Information (AFLI)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- Association for Progressive Communicators (APC)
- Bioline International
- Bookshare
- British Council – Myanmar
- Centre for Internet and Society (India)
- Citizen's Services & Libraries, City of Aarhus, Denmark
- cOAlition S
- Coko Foundation
- COMMUNIA
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Corporación Innovarte
- Creative Commons
- DAISY Consortium
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), DuraSpace
- Education International
- Fundación Karisma
- GÉANT
- Gigabit Library Network (GLN)
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Google Scholar
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- IEEE
- Information Power
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Council of Museums (ICOM)
- International Council on Archives (ICA)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- Internet Society
- Libraries Development for the Local Government Management Agency in Ireland
- Kenya National Library Service
- Knowledge Ecology International (KEI)
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- Maendeleo Foundation
- MentorNations
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Uganda
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- ORCID
- OA2020
- Peer 2 Peer University
- People Centered Internet (PCI)
- Program on Information Justice and Intellectual Property (PIJIP)
- Progress Foundation Romania
- Public Library Association (PLA) – American Library Association
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- Rectors' Committee, National Education Policy Commission, Ministry of Education of Myanmar
- Right to Research Coalition
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- Tactical Tech
- The International Relations Round Table (IRRT), American Library Association
- The Library and Information Association of Zambia (LIAZ)
- Ubiquity Press
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- UNESCO
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- Wikimedia Deutschland
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working relationship

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 63 partners through European Commission-funded projects: Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Advance, and Strengthening Research Management and Open Science Capacities of HEIs in Moldova and Armenia (Minerva).

WHERE WE WORK

In 2020, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 38 countries and ran projects in an additional 15 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

STAY CONNECTED

eifl.net

@EIFLnet

eifl-net

GET IN TOUCH

Mail: Mindaugo str. 23, LT-03214 Vilnius, Lithuania

Tel: +370 5 2080409 **Email:** info@eifl.net

For more information about EIFL and our work visit eifl.net